

Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Ga(III) by Some Uni- and Polyvalent Cations vis-a-vis their Influence on the Kinetics of Electrode Reaction of Ga(III)

ASHOK KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, St. John's College, Agra

and

KAILASH CHANDRA and MUKHTAR SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002

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Suppression of polarographic maximum of Ga(III), which falls in the category of the negative maximum of the first kind, has been attempted using some uni- and polyvalent cations, viz, Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , La^{3+} , Nb^{5+} and Pr^{3+} as suppressors. The extent to which the electrode reaction of Ga(III) is rendered more irreversible from the position in the absence of suppressors at the point of just suppression, is suggested as the criterion for determining the efficacy of a suppressor. Based on this approach the order of efficacies of uni- and poly-valent cations in the suppression of the negative maximum of Ga(III) has been established as $\text{La}^{3+} > \text{Nb}^{5+} > \text{Pr}^{3+} > \text{Al}^{3+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Li}^+$.

ZELTZER¹ studied the polarographic behaviour of Ga(III) in HCl and reported the maximum at -1.1 V vs SCE. The maximum of Ga(III) was reported at about -1.5 V vs SCE from an ammoniacal base solution. This was further studied by Zuman² in a mixture of 1 M ammonium hydroxide and 1 M ammonium chloride solutions. Challenger³ observed a single well-defined wave for Ga(III) in KCl. Bolsanbekova and Zabrava⁴ studied the polarographic behaviour of Ga(III) in an oxalate base electrolyte as a function of the pH of the solution and the concentration of the depolarizer. Kataeva *et al*⁵ studied the oscillo-polarographic behaviour of Ga(III) in 0.1 M sodium salicylate and found the electrode reaction diffusion-controlled and irreversible. Recently, Dubey and Singh⁶ have investigated the effect of temperature on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reaction of Ga(III). Literature reveals that the suppression of negative maximum of Ga(III) by uni- and polyvalent cations has not been studied so far.

In the present paper an attempt has been made to suppress the maximum of Ga(III) by some uni- and poly-valent cations and then to study the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ga(III) as a function of concentration of the cations from the stage where the maximum just disappears. The order of relative efficacies of cations on the basis of α_n values, calculated at the point of just suppression, has also been determined.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of Ga(III) [using $\text{Ga}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Fluka A.R.] in the final solution to be polarographed was kept at $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and that of the supporting electrolyte, NaNO_3 , at 0.1 M.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal, CLO2A) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal, PL50) was used for measuring the potential and the current, respectively. All measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Deoxygenation of the solutions was done by passing a steady stream of purified nitrogen gas through the solution. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The dropping mercury electrode (dme) consisted of a standard capillary (E. H. Sargent & Co.) which had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M NaNO_3 , open circuit): $h_{\text{corr}} = 71.45$ cm; $m = 2.2$ mg/sec; $t = 3.1$ sec; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.03$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}.

The number of electrons 'n' involved in the reduction of Ga(III) was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon⁷. This gave the value of 'n' equal to 3. Knowing the value of 'n', Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of 'D', the diffusion coefficient of Ga(III) at various concentrations of uni- and poly-valent

cations. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and k_{ph}^0) were calculated by Koutecky's method^{8,9}.

prerequisite. This actually happens in the present system (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

In representative Fig. 1, curve 1 shows the polarogram of Ga(III) in 0.1 M NaNO₃. Successive polarograms (curves 2-6) were recorded in the presence of increasing concentrations of Pr(III). The first kind polarographic maximum of Ga(III) under the chosen experimental conditions appears at -1.36 V (vs SCE). This lies well on the negative side of the potential of the electro-capillary zero under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{1/2}$ of Ga(III) also lies on the negative side of the electro-capillary zero, the maximum of Ga(III) is of negative polarity¹⁰.

Singh *et al*¹¹ have put forward that for the suppression of negative maximum by adsorptive cations (like those used here) a positive shift of the maximum (E_{max}) prior to the final suppression is a

Fig. 1. C-V curves of Ga(III) in the presence of increasing concentrations of Pr³⁺.
1. 0.0 M; 2. 0.2 × 10⁻⁴ M; 3. 1.8 × 10⁻⁴ M; 4. 2.4 × 10⁻⁴ M
5. 2.8 × 10⁻⁴ M; 6. 3.2 × 10⁻⁴ M.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Ga(III) IN THE PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF UNI- AND POLY-VALENT CATIONS

[Cation] M	-E _{max} V (SCE)	-E _{1/2} V (SCE)	i _{max} μA	i _d μA	Slope mV	D × 10 ⁶ cm ² /sec	αn _a	k _{ph} ⁰ cm/sec
Li ⁺								
× 10 ³								
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	1.28	—	25.48	—	—	—	—	—
8.0	1.26	—	11.89	—	—	—	—	—
*9.0	No max	1.130	—	10.87	110	6.98	0.41	2.81 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
20.0	"	1.138	—	9.51	118	4.89	0.38	1.30 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
40.0	"	1.142	—	6.79	124	2.49	0.36	3.54 × 10 ⁻¹¹
Na ⁺								
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
1.1	1.34	—	32.28	—	—	—	—	—
1.6	1.30	—	12.23	—	—	—	—	—
*1.7	No max	1.160	—	10.87	118	6.98	0.50	1.00 × 10 ⁻¹¹
3.0	"	1.165	—	9.17	120	4.54	0.41	1.65 × 10 ⁻¹²
5.0	"	1.200	—	7.82	125	3.81	0.38	4.28 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
K ⁺								
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
4.0	1.28	—	20.05	—	—	—	—	—
8.0	1.26	—	12.91	—	—	—	—	—
*9.0	No max	1.143	—	11.21	102	6.80	0.43	7.67 × 10 ⁻¹²
32.0	"	1.155	—	9.17	105	4.55	0.40	1.20 × 10 ⁻¹²
48.0	"	1.170	—	7.81	110	3.30	0.38	2.21 × 10 ⁻¹³
Ba ²⁺								
× 10 ³								
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
0.1	1.32	—	27.19	—	—	—	—	—
0.4	1.26	—	10.87	—	—	—	—	—
*0.8	No max	1.150	—	10.53	125	5.99	0.52	5.67 × 10 ⁻¹¹
1.6	"	1.160	—	9.18	130	4.55	0.49	4.47 × 10 ⁻¹²
4.0	"	1.170	—	7.81	138	3.30	0.43	4.49 × 10 ⁻¹³
Sr ²⁺								
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
0.1	1.30	—	25.14	—	—	—	—	—
0.9	1.26	—	10.87	—	—	—	—	—
*1.1	No max	1.129	—	9.85	100	5.25	0.51	3.11 × 10 ⁻¹¹
2.0	"	1.132	—	8.83	102	4.22	0.48	1.35 × 10 ⁻¹²
3.0	"	1.135	—	7.47	110	3.02	0.46	5.91 × 10 ⁻¹³

(Table 1 Contd.)

				Ca ²⁺				
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
0.2	1.32	—	25.14	—	—	—	—	—
0.8	1.26	—	11.21	—	—	—	—	—
*1.0	No max	1.140	—	10.87	118	6.38	0.51	2.10 × 10 ⁻¹¹
1.5	"	1.145	—	8.83	124	4.21	0.48	1.36 × 10 ⁻¹²
2.0	"	1.150	—	7.81	128	3.29	0.46	7.11 × 10 ⁻¹³
				Mg ²⁺				
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
0.2	1.28	—	20.39	—	—	—	—	—
0.9	1.26	—	10.87	—	—	—	—	—
1.1	No max	1.130	—	10.19	120	5.62	0.56	3.87 × 10 ⁻¹³
4.0	"	1.140	—	7.47	130	3.02	0.53	1.03 × 10 ⁻¹³
5.0	"	1.145	—	6.79	135	2.50	0.51	5.40 × 10 ⁻¹⁶
				Al ³⁺				
× 10 ³								
0.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
0.1	1.30	—	25.82	—	—	—	—	—
0.3	1.26	—	14.95	—	—	—	—	—
*0.4	No max	1.135	—	13.25	92	9.49	0.59	1.63 × 10 ⁻¹³
0.7	"	1.140	—	10.53	94	5.99	0.56	1.03 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.0	"	1.142	—	9.85	96	5.25	0.52	6.50 × 10 ⁻¹³
				La ³⁺				
0.0	1.36	—	41.25	—	—	—	—	—
0.1	1.34	—	29.56	—	—	—	—	—
0.2	1.26	—	10.53	—	—	—	—	—
*0.3	No max	1.150	—	9.51	70	4.90	0.77	1.58 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
0.4	"	1.151	—	8.83	72	4.20	0.75	6.92 × 10 ⁻¹⁷
5.4	"	1.153	—	7.48	75	3.02	0.72	3.72 × 10 ⁻¹⁷
				Nb ⁵⁺				
0.0	1.36	—	41.25	—	—	—	—	—
0.4	1.32	—	34.66	—	—	—	—	—
1.8	1.22	—	15.29	—	—	—	—	—
*1.9	No max	1.120	—	13.59	78	9.92	0.71	3.89 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
2.2	"	1.121	—	12.57	80	8.54	0.68	2.80 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
3.0	"	1.122	—	11.55	83	7.21	0.63	1.70 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
				Pr ³⁺				
0.0	1.36	—	41.25	—	—	—	—	—
0.2	1.32	—	30.24	—	—	—	—	—
1.8	1.26	—	14.95	—	—	—	—	—
2.4	1.24	—	12.91	—	—	—	—	—
*2.8	No max	1.125	—	10.87	95	6.39	0.62	4.79 × 10 ⁻¹³
3.2	"	1.130	—	10.19	98	5.62	0.60	6.23 × 10 ⁻¹⁴

* Concentration at which the maximum just disappears.

Various criteria¹²⁻¹⁴ of the irreversibility indicate that the polarographic reduction of Ga(III) is totally irreversible in the presence of uni- and poly-valent cations. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{t,h}^0$) have been calculated by Koutecky's method at the point of just suppression of the maximum of Ga(III) and beyond it. A perusal of Table 1 shows that the product αn_a decreases with increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations. The maximum value of αn_a at the stage of just suppression of the maximum is ≈ 0.8 . Since for a totally irreversible process, as the present one is, α should¹⁵ be less than 0.5, a value of $\alpha n_a \approx 0.8$ would lead to the conclusion that $n_a \approx 2$. However, according to Meites¹⁶ only a single electron can be transferred at a time and a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too close

to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurement. Thus, whether n_a is 1 or 2, the change in αn_a values, which at no stage vary by a factor of 2 between successive values can only be due to a change in α . It is thus concluded that it is the α which is decreasing. α , the transfer coefficient, signifies¹⁷ the fraction of applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $Ga^{3+} + 3e \rightarrow Ga$. A decrease in the value of α implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words the electrode reaction of Ga(III) is rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations. A decrease in the value of $k_{t,h}^0$ with increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations also lends support to this conclusion.

At the stage where the maximum of Ga(III) just disappears, the order of α_{n_s} value signifies¹¹ the extent to which the addition of uni- and poly-valent cations renders the electrode reaction of Ga(III) more irreversible from the stage when no suppressor was added. In other words a cation for which α_{n_s} has got a higher value at the point of just suppression will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ga(III). On this basis the order of efficacies of various uni- and poly-valent cations has been established as $\text{La}^{3+} > \text{Nb}^{5+} > \text{Pr}^{3+} > \text{Al}^{3+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Li}^+$. Thus, La^{3+} eliminates the maximum of Ga(III) with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electron transfer. This order of relative efficacies of uni- and poly-valent cations, found on the basis of α_{n_s} values, is interestingly identical with that obtained on the basis of molarity scale.

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